

**Global Observatory for Gender Equality & Sport
Zenodo Community Curation Policy**

Name of The Document:	Zenodo Community Curation Policy		
Description of The Document:	This document outlines the GO curation policy for GO Zenodo community.		
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Purpose and Scope

The Global Observatory for Gender Equality and Sport (GO) community on Zenodo serves as a repository for digital research outputs related to gender equality and sport, including but not limited to physical activity, physical education, and sport (PEPAS). The repository welcomes contributions from the GO and other relevant stakeholders.

All content within this community is governed by [Zenodo's general policies](#) and [Terms of Use](#).

Community Management

The GO community is managed and curated by GO staff. To learn more about the GO, visit <https://genderequalitysport.org/>.

Content Scope and Accessibility

The GO community accepts digital research objects that align with its thematic focus on gender equality and sport. Submissions should adhere to the principle of "**as open as possible, as closed as necessary**", while also striving for [FAIR data principles](#) (**Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable**). GO also adopts the [Inclusive Data Charter](#) principles as a guiding framework and seeks to incorporate its principles in all its data efforts.

Both **public and restricted** content (with or without embargo or access request) may be accepted.

Submission and Moderation

Any user may submit records directly to the GO community on Zenodo.

Submissions undergo **moderation** by GO staff to ensure compliance with minimal metadata requirements and accuracy. GO staff reserves the **right to decline** records that do not meet the community's requirements.

Records created by the GO itself are also subject to the same curation process.

Minimal Metadata Requirements

All records in the GO community must comply with the following **minimal metadata** standards:

- **Visibility:** Both public and restricted records (with or without embargo and/or access request) are permitted.
- **Resource Types:** All digital research object types are accepted.
- **Licensing:** All records must specify a **license**.
- **Creators:** All creators should be identified using a **persistent identifier** (e.g., ORCID), and affiliations should be provided.
- **Description:** The record description field must provide relevant and clear information.
- **Title:** The record title must be **clear and relevant**.
- **Keywords:** The record must specify relevant keywords. It is recommended to use 2-6 keywords.

Review and Curation

All submissions undergo a **curation check** to verify compliance with this policy. GO staff will review and approve records before inclusion in the community.

Community curators may edit metadata as needed without prior notice. Curators may remove records that:

- Do not comply with this policy.
- Are deemed of insufficient quality.

Policy Updates

This curation policy is subject to change at any time by the community owner, without prior notice.